

VALKYRIES

D1.10 Impact Creation Report

Reference Number: D1.10

Ed/Rev: A/1

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Other Contributors: All Partners

Date: 25/01/2023

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101020676

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Document Changes Record

Edit./Rev.	Date	Chapters	Reason for change
A/0	16/09/2022	All	Original Document
A/1	19/01/2023		Comments from general project review consolidated report are addressed. New text and changes from previous version are highlighted in yellow for easy identification. Corrected value with real information regarding participants Joint events, round tables. Added published scientific publication. Updated Dissemination KPIs table.

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1. Executive Summary

VALKYRIES develops, integrates and demonstrates capabilities for enabling immediate and coordinated emergency response including search and rescue, security and health, in scenarios of natural/provoked catastrophes with multiple victims, with special application in cases in which several regions or countries are affected and hence greater interoperability being required.

As it is well understood the communication and dissemination in VALKYRIES plays a pivotal role. At month six (M6) the consortium released the Communication and Dissemination Strategy (D1.9) where the overall C&D strategy was drawn, planning its evaluation in a series of deliverables in M12 and M24 to track the impact generated by the consortium endeavours towards the accomplishment of the C&D goals. In this context, the present document drives the initial effort to identify relevant lines of work which realization generate a positive impact in the performance indicators defined in D1.9. This deliverable is thus aimed on sharing the consortium vision towards the forwarding direction the C&D strategy is taking, which is presented in the form of reported joint and individual actions carried out by the VALKYRIES partners up to the current stage of the project, accounting dissemination and communication activities undertaken during the first year of the project as well.

Among the performed actions, the website reorganization has been possible with active participation of the consortium members, raising the importance of a strong web presence across the time. This online presence is intrinsically bound to the social media platforms, so that the consortium underpinned the basis for measuring analytics reflecting the impact of such platforms within the audience. In addition, external visibility has been pushed forward by the release of scientific publications framed in the research lines coped by VALKYRIES, as well as informative publications targeted to EMS practitioners. Furthermore, general-purposed communications broadcasted on the media in the form of press releases has been accounted in this report as their impact on the general audience is far more reaching. The liaison preliminary efforts conclude the tracked activities of this report, opening room to the next steps planned by the consortium members.

At the end of this deliverable, the next steps and the main concluding remarks are provided. They stress the position of the consortium during this first year in the project timeline, along with a critical revision of the future lines of work ahead in the next reporting period (M13-M24).

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: Impact Creation Report

Deliverable Id: D1.10

Deliverable Title Abbreviation: D1.10

Name of lead participant: Indra (IND)

Name of Contributors: All partners

Type: Report (R)

Dissemination Level: Public (PU)

Proposed Classification Level: Non-Restricted

Reporting Conditions: Funding Requirement (FR)

Linked project Work Package: WP1 - Project Management and Communication

Linked project tasks: T1.3 - Consultation Strategy and Liaison with European/national authorities / T1.4 - Dissemination strategy

Action: Design

Status: Second release, version A/1

Document Layout: VALKYRIES official template

Details: This specification applies to the project VALKYRIES: Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters funded under the SU-DRS03-2018-2019-2020 (IA), subtopic 3 Grant Agreement of the Horizon 2020 (H2020) tendering conditions.

Deliverable D1.10 is framed into the project tasks T1.3 and T1.4, having the purpose to report the undertaken efforts to generate impact on the communication & dissemination strategy. The reported actions considered here are accounted in the reporting period from M1 to M12 of the project, as several partners' undergone efforts to disseminate their involvement in VALKYRIES among different audiences.

3. Document and Project Scope

3.1. Project Overview

The increasing frequency and intensity of natural and human-made disasters [1]- [2] requires policies aimed at tackling these risks through preventive, preparedness, response and recovery actions. Increasing the resilience of infrastructures, ecosystems and society in EU is an important strand of disaster risk management work.

It is from this need that VALKYRIES was born, a project co-financed by the European Union (EU) under the framework of the H2020 program. It is within the field of security, specifically in disaster-resilient societies under the topic *Pre-normative research and demonstration for disaster-resilient societies: First aids vehicles deployment, training, maintenance, logistic and remote centralized coordination means*.

The project will develop a methodology for tracking and analysing the needs for standardisation and harmonisation as regards the tools for supporting EU disaster resiliency. Specifically, it will develop, integrate and demonstrate capabilities for enabling immediate and coordinated emergency response, including for search and rescue, security and health, in scenarios of natural/provoked catastrophes with multiple victims, with special application in cases in several regions or countries.

In order to develop the project, a multidisciplinary consortium has been created with key partners from industry (large companies and SMEs), universities, research centres and end users, which jointly have defined a series of work streams and international and cross-sectorial use cases that give the project great value.

3.2. Document Structure

The document is organized as follows:

Section 1 presents the executive summary of the deliverable content.

Section 2 summarizes identifying information about the deliverable

Section 3 introduces the document and project scope.

Section 4 gives an overview on the communication activities carried out during the reporting period and the current status of the VALKYRIES' online presence.

Section 5 gives an overview on the dissemination activities carried out during the reporting period.

Section 6 reports the status of the liaison actions carried out with related EU projects.

Section 7 sets the next C&D actions to be developed during the second year of the project.

Section 8 closes the document with the conclusions.

4. Report on Communication

This section will provide an overview of the progress made during the first year of project in the communication activities of the VALKYRIES Project.

In M6, *D1.9 Communication and Dissemination Strategies* was delivered, where the Consortium's partners have included their individual and joint communication and dissemination plans, as well as the main activities to be carried out between M1-M12 and the detected activities, conferences and high impact journals for next year. In order to measure the progress and the success of these activities, a series of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were defined in D1.9 and the following have already been fulfilled or are in progress, as can be seen in Table 1.

Communication KPIs				
Activity	Description	Expected impact	KPIs	Progress Status
Design logo and presentation templates	Professional logo. Professional presentation template to be used by partners.	Visual identity and branding of the project; unified experience for the targeted audience.	Logo and templates available in professional quality by M2.	100%
Project fact sheet	Double-sided A4 page containing basic information on the project.	Provision of instant information about the project.	500+ readers reached.	100%
Project press releases	Showcase the progress and the results	Inform stakeholders, increase awareness and disseminate information	5+ Press releases per year	50%
Project newsletters	Showcase the progress and the results	Inform stakeholders, increase awareness and disseminate information	2+ newsletters per years	50%
Project website	A website, providing information about the project, the demos and the results to target audiences.	Main online information point; communication of project news, events results; liaisons with other initiatives, projects through links.	An average of 500+ visitors per year.	50%
Social Media channels	Regular sharing of news on activities and results as well as interaction with target audiences via social media.	Increasing visibility to stakeholders; direct communication mechanism between social media users and Consortium.	500+ followers on Twitter/LinkedIn	28%
			100+ tweets on Twitter	70%
			100+ Posts on LinkedIn.	30%
Joint events, round tables	Events co-organized with targeted stakeholders or where VALKYRIES will be invited to present its work and vision.	Information exchange and dissemination; increase awareness.	500+ participants reached in total over 24 months	64%
White papers	Posters/banners to present the project's concept; Flyers with general project information; ad-hoc information at selected events.	Communication of results and information provision at events; ad-hoc diffusion of information based on	2,000+ readers reached via printed and electronic copies.	100%

Communication KPIs				
Activity	Description	Expected impact	KPIs	Progress Status
		identified opportunities.		
Demonstration, show cases, exhibitions	Events where VALKYRIES will communicate its results through demonstrations.	Attraction of target audiences and making them aware of the VALKYRIES solutions' benefits.	2,000+ visitors reached in total over 24 months	0%

Table 1 - Progress in Communication KPIs

The activities performed in the reporting period covering M1 to M12 are described in the following subsections. These activities also include the design and creation of a project identity, logo and documentary templates (for more information refer to D1.9).

4.1. Website

4.1.1. Website Structure

The VALKYRIES website is accessible from M1 of the project so pushing forward the project's online presence among the general audience. Within this reporting period tough, several topics of improvement were identified so that they motivated changes not only in the web structure but also concerning the content. The reorganized sitemap is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – VALKYRIES' website structure

By an internal consultation within the consortium, partner's feedback disclosed a number of improvement topics directly impacting the audience reach out by presenting better information and along with a more appealing design as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – VALKYRIES' website main page

The purpose of each website section is better explained in Table 2.

Menu	Description
The project	Presents the VALKYRIES highlights along with the project objectives. The three submenus' contents have been rewritten with more engaging takeaways, explaining the project work streams (KARA, HERJA, EIR) associated with WP4, 5 and 6, respectively, the SIGRUN reference integration and the four use cases that will take place at the end of the project.
Consortium	Despite the improvement in presenting information from the consortium partners, the External Advisory Board members are presented.
Dissemination	Awareness of the public dissemination activities of VALKYRIES will impact positively at widening the visibility of the project in terms of communication and dissemination outcomes among the target stakeholders. At the time of this writing, two submenus for categorizing dissemination information are considered: publications and participation in events.
Resources	This section makes room for additional categories purposed to provide visitors further sources of information including News, the project Newsletters and some Demo resources in order to get feedback for the audience and showcase interactive material

Menu	Description
Contact us	VALKYRIES contact information remains offering an official email account to address any type of inquiries or comments for the general audience, as well as a direct access to the project Twitter and LinkedIn profiles.

Table 2 – Website tabs

4.1.2. Updates

In M1, the project website was created and published (<https://www.valkyries-h2020.eu>). After gathering partners' comments and suggestions, a second version of the website was designed, and republished in M5. The website complies with current legislation. The legal notice and privacy policy of the website is available to the user. In addition, it has undergone a security audit with a favourable rating for both the web service and the hosting server. Finally, in order to upload all the multimedia files of events, conferences, etc. that include the presence of natural persons to the web, the corresponding image declaration of consents have been compiled.

During the reporting period a total of 4 updates have been made in the VALKYRIES's website on M5, M8, M9 and M12. These updates include:

- Second webpage version
- Typos correction
- New events carried out on the "Events" tab
- New publications carried out on the "Publications" tab
- News that have taken place on the "News" tab
- Newsletters - Issues 1 and 2 on the "Newsletters" tab
- New "Demo" tab
- General content updates

4.1.3. Web statistics

A seamless collection of web statistics is performed by the Matomo web analytics platform (<https://matomo.org>). Among the possible capabilities to leverage, the acquisition of visits counters, navigation behaviours, geographical distribution of web accesses and other similar features have already been used.

Figure 3 shows a graphical representation of the number of visits to the VALKYRIES website across the period covered between October 2021 (M1) and September 2022 (M12). The peak number of visits has been attained at July 5th, 2022 with 44 visits.

Figure 3 – Website visits over time

On the other hand, the geographical distribution of visitors of the VALKYRIES website is depicted in Figure 4. Table 3 shows the 3 continents with the highest percentages of visitors. There, it can be noted that the highest concentration of visits comes from European sources, mainly Spain (338 visits), Greece (116 visits) and Italy (60 visits). Interestingly, the second continent with the

greatest number of visits is North-America with 267 visits coming from the United States and the third continent is Asia with 35 visits from China. Within the reporting period (October 2021 – September 2022), total of **1117 visits** have been registered, accounting 2.819 page views in total.

Continent	Percentage of visitors
Europe	71%
North-America	24.3%
Asia	4%

Table 3 – Continents with the highest percentage of visits

Visitor Map

Figure 4 – Website visitors' geographical distribution

4.2. Social media

In M2, a social media account for the project was created on LinkedIn and on Twitter. To date, VALKYRIES has presence on social media platforms progressively gaining more presence as the number of followers increases. Table 4 summarizes basic metrics of the social media platforms whereas Figure 5 and Figure 6 display the current frontmatter of the Twitter and LinkedIn accounts, respectively, adapted to the corporate identity styles defined by VALKYRIES.

Description	Twitter	LinkedIn
Total number of followers	44	95
Entries/posts	70+	30+
Impressions (last 28 days)	269	652
Best Engagement rate (last 365 days)	36%	48%

Table 4 - VALKYRIES numbers on social media platforms

Figure 5 - Twitter frontpage

Figure 6 - LinkedIn frontpage

4.3. Events participation

The list of events attended by partners of the VALKYRIES consortium, and the activities performed on each are described in Table 5.

Event Name	Country	Date	Description
ENISE	Spain	19-20 Oct. 2021	Attendance of the project coordinator and the C&D Manager to the ENISE event (Spain) organized and invited by INCIBE who signed a LoS for VALKYRIES. During the event, key entities of the cybersecurity industry that was present. https://www.incibe.es/enise
FEINDEF	Spain	5 Nov. 2021	Attendance of the project coordinator and the C&D Manager to the FEINDEF event (Spain) organized in IFEMA and invited by CDTI to present the VALKYRIES project on a round table. https://www.feindef.com/conferencias.asp
AIMES H2020 Event	Portugal	17 Dec. 2021	Presentation of VALKYRIES SP-PT Use case at the AIMES H2020 event in Portugal organized by EDGE and HESE. https://aimes-eurostars.eu/event/aimes-final-pilot/
Joint Event on Crisis Management of the MEDEA and the FIRE-IN projects	Greece	18 Jan. 2022	Virtual attendance at the Joint Event on Crisis Management of the MEDEA and the FIRE-IN projects organized by KEMEA. https://www.medeaproject.eu/rdi-days-tcp-4/
Coffee Chat with U.S. Embassy	Spain	8 Mar. 2022	VALKYRIES' PC was invited by the US embassy to be part of a round table together with the Spanish delegate and national expert - Maite Boyero Egido - and the Chief Inspector of the Spanish National Police - José Francisco López. The event took place in an online format and hosted by Angel Turrin and Cameron Werker, representatives of the U.S. Commercial Service. Link to Project website
Projects to Policy Seminar (PPS)	Belgium	30 Jun.-1 Jul. 2022	The PPS took place in Brussels. The event was co-hosted by DG HOME and REA from the European Commission and PC Juan-Román Martínez was invited to participate and disseminate the project among other initiatives financed by the EU. https://eu.eventscloud.com/website/7112/home/

Table 5 – Events attended by VALKYRIES' partners

4.4. Press Releases

VALKYRIES has gained attention from the general audience, present in several press releases where the aims and project envisioned capabilities have taken prominence. Evidences of the VALKYRIES presence on digital media, even from early stages of the project are shown in Table 6. From one side, Table 6 shows press releases that have an internal origin, that is, they have been published by the entities that are part of the consortium. However, VALKYRIES has called the attention of entities external to the project, both civil and military, who have carried out press releases and small communication articles.

Internal Sources		
Source	Release Date	URL
Particle's corporate website	Jan. 2022	https://particle-summary.pt/wp/2022/01/26/valkyries-harmonizing-response-and-procedures-for-emergencies-and-first-aid-vehicles-deployment/
ISEMI's corporate website	Jan. 2022	https://www.isemi.sk/en_GB/aktivity/
Indra's corporate website	Feb. 2022	https://www.indracompany.com/en/indra/valkyries-harmonization-pre-standardization-equipment-training-tactical-coordinated-procedures
Novotec's corporate website	Feb. 2022	https://www.novotec.es/global/es/news/novotec-participa-en-el-proyecto-europeo-valkyries-para-la-gestion-del-riesgo-de-catastrofes
TASSICA's corporate website	Feb. 2022	https://www.tassica.com/index.php/sala-de-prensa/tassica-emergency-training-research-s-a-forma-p
Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna's corporate website	May 2022	https://www.santannapisa.it/it/news/armonizzare-e-standardizzare-le-procedure-situazioni-emergenziali-il-primo-general-meeting-del
External Sources		
Source	Release Date	URL
EC Horizon Magazine	Oct. 2021	https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/horizon-magazine/battling-wildfires-behind-scenes
AES (Asociación Española de empresas de Seguridad)	Jan. 2022	https://www.aesseguridad.es/boletin/80/index.html#features/
CRISPRO	Mar. 2022	https://crispro.eu/valkyries/
Red Seguridad	Apr. 2022	https://www.seguritecnia.es/revistas/seg/494/108/index.html
Infodefensa	Jun. 2022	https://www.infodefensa.com/texto-diario/mostrar/3786590/ocho-paises-entre-espana-seran-primeros-probar-proyecto-valkyries
The research Council of Norway	Unknown	https://prosjektbanken.forskingsradet.no/en/project/EU/101020676?Kilde=EU&distribution=Ar&chart=bar&calcType=funding&Sprak=no&sortBy=date&sortOrder=desc&resultCount=30&offset=0&LTP.1=LTP2+Styrket+konkurranseskraft+og+innovasjonsevne&source=EU&projectId=951933

Table 6 – VALKYRIES presence on digital media from internal and external sources

Figure 7 illustrates some examples of external media coverage attained by VALKYRIES.

The screenshot shows a news article on the Sant'Anna website. The article title is "Armonizzare e standardizzare le procedure in situazioni emergenziali: il primo general meeting del progetto H2020-VALKYRIES ospitato alla Scuola Sant'Anna, che partecipa con il LIDER Lab. Risultati preliminari presto presentati in prestigiosa conferenza". The date is 19.05.2022. There is a photo of a group of people standing outdoors. The website header includes the Sant'Anna logo and navigation menus for Ateneo, Formazione, Ricerca, Terza Missione, and Internazionale. An "Info per" button is also visible.

The screenshot shows the Tassica website. The header includes the Tassica logo (EMERGENCY, TRAINING & RESEARCH S.A.), a phone number (T. 0034 921 11 93 88), and a navigation menu with buttons for FORMACIÓN, I+D+I, LA EMPRESA, and CONTACTO. The main content area features a blue header with a circuit pattern and a navigation bar with links: Datos básicos, ¿Quiénes somos?, ¿Qué nos diferencia?, and Sala de prensa. The main headline reads "TASSICA EMERGENCY, TRAINING & RESEARCH S.A. forma parte del Proyecto Europeo H2020 VALKYRIES." Below this is a date "04/02/2022" and a paragraph in Spanish: "España, además de liderar el proyecto, tiene una gran representación ya que cuenta con grandes empresas como Indra y Novotec (de la multinacional App+), nuestra empresa TASSICA y un centro de investigación como es la universidad de Murcia." To the right, there is a green box for "MÁSTER URGENCIAS, EMERGENCIAS Y CATÁSTROFES" and a blue box for "Casos de éxito" featuring "SAMER Protección Civil".

Figure 7 - Examples of VALKYRIES press releases

4.5. Communication material

In addition to the PowerPoint and Word templates that were designed following the graphic line of the project (refer to D1.9), additional communication material has been developed:

- A factsheet of the Project in triptych format (see Figure 8 right) that has the basic information about VALKYRIES and that has been distributed to more than 2000 people in several events such as the CPDP congress, the RISE-SD symposium and the ARES congress.
- A rollup to be displayed as visual appeal at conferences and events (see Figure 8 left) has also been designed and used, for example, during the VALKYRIES presentation in the RISE-SD symposium.

Figure 8 – (Left) Project rollup and (right up) front and (right down) back of the Project Factsheet in triptych format.

In addition to the previous material, some advertising elements have been generated and distributed in which the VALKYRIES logo appears, such as the pens and USB flash drives shown in Figure 9. These elements serve as an attraction for the public in those fairs in which a partner of the project has a stand with information about the project, as it was done during the Bulgarian Defence fair.

Figure 9 – Tryptic and merchandising

4.6. Newsletters

Newsletter aim to inform stakeholders about project developments and advances. At least two newsletters per year are planned to be issued on the dates indicated below:

The first newsletter was released in M8, published in the project website and posted in Twitter and LinkedIn and the next issue is going to be released in September 2022 (M12). During the second year of project there will be two more issues, one in March 2023 and the final newsletter in September 2023. The Consortium members are encouraged to include the VALKYRIES newsletter in their institutional newsletters and communication documents in order to increase local coverage.

5. Report on Dissemination

This section will provide an overview of the progress made during the first year of project in the dissemination activities of the VALKYRIES Project. As a summary, in Table 7 we present the main actions that have been carried out between M1 and M12 and that are part of the progress described in this section.

In the same way as with the communication strategy, in deliverable *D1.9 Communication and Dissemination Strategies* released in M6, both individual and joint dissemination strategies were defined. Likewise, a series of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were defined to measure the progress and success of these activities.

Dissemination KPIs				
Activity	Description	Expected impact	KPIs	Progress Status
VALKYRIES Workshops	VALKYRIES workshops in M6/M12/M24 will be organized.	Information exchange, dissemination; awareness.	3 workshops 30+ attendees per workshop. 25%+ of women per workshop	33%
Legal / Ethical Workshops	L/E workshops in M6/M12/M18/M24 will be organized.	Sensitize the ethical-legal framework	4 workshops 15+ attendees per workshop. 25%+ of women per workshop	50%
Standardization Workshops	workshops in M6/M12/M18/M24 will be organized.	Discussion of the VALKYRIES results on the regulation, standardization, certification and harmonization issues	4 workshops 15+ attendees per workshop. 25%+ of women per workshop	25%
Demonstration Workshops	Demonstration workshops in M6/M12/M24 will be organized	Discussion of the VALKYRIES demonstration scenarios definition, planning and execution	3 workshops 30+ attendees per workshop. 25%+ of women per workshop	33%
Liaisons	Liaisons with national and EU projects	Run liaison initiatives related with other H2020 projects to boost areas of application	5+ liaison with EU projects	20%
Publications	Scientific and high-level publications	Contribute to scientific communities, dissemination; awareness	5+ Scientific, publications with high impact 2+ Open access publications	40%
Conferences	Scientific and high-level conferences	Contribute to scientific communities, dissemination; awareness	5+ Scientific conferences with high impact	40%
Experts involved	Stakeholders committed with external advisory boards	Receive impartial scientific advice, support the PST and	5+ experts active involved per EAB	100%

Dissemination KPIs				
Activity	Description	Expected impact	KPIs	Progress Status
		advise the Consortium on social, environmental, technological, legal and economic factors that may influence the innovation management of VALKYRIES		

Table 7 - Progress in Dissemination KPIs

The activities performed in the reporting period covering M1 to M12 are described in the following subsections.

5.1. Workshops

In this section we describe the workshops organized by one or more partners of the consortium in the reporting period. These workshops correspond to those specified in Table 7. Table 8 summarizes relevant information about the workshops carried out. The total number of EAB experts who attended the first round of workshops was seven (7), this value corresponds to the measure of the KPI "Experts Involved".

Workshop	Date	Context	Location	Organizers
VALKYRIES and Demonstration	March 30 th , 2022	Project Workshop	Virtual	Indra (IND), SUMMA112 (SUM), ISEMI (ISE), Bulgarian Defence Institute (BDI), University of South-eastern Norway USN)
Standardization	March 31 th , 2022	Project Workshop	Virtual	Novotec (NOV)
Legal and Ethical	May 25 th , 2022	Computer Privacy and Data Protection (CPDP) conferences	La Cave, Brussels, Belgium	Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna (SSA), Indra (IND)

Table 8 – Relevant Workshop Information

5.1.1. 1st VALKYRIES and Demonstration Workshops

Indra (IND) organized on March 30th the first VALKYRIES and Demonstration workshops. The event was held in virtual format and had the aim of bringing together main stakeholders of the emergency sector (such as Eliance, AFCEA, etc.), Industrial stakeholders and universities, into an open discussion pointed to analyse the current status of the emergency services in terms of cross-sector and cross-border interoperability, their view and implementation of disruptive technologies and the role of VALKYRIES within this landscape. In total there were 55 attendees who connected to the workshops, of which 24% were women.

The progress made in the first 6 months of the project was presented in terms of the project requirements gathered, definition of the demonstration scenarios and strategy used in the standardization tasks. The EAB provided their valuable views on the status of the project and the work methodology used.

Figure 10 – Pictures of the VALKYRIES and Demonstration workshops

As a preparatory activity before the workshops, the requirements defined during the first months of the project were sent to the members of the EAB. Thus, for approximately three weeks before the event, they were able to review and analyse the requirements. Subsequently, as a consultation activity, a survey was sent to the members of the EAB in order for them to put down their impressions and recommendations in writing, both for those who were able to attend the workshops and for those who were not. This last group was provided with all the presentations of the WSs.

Following the agenda, shown in Figure 11, the Communication and Dissemination Manager Marta I. García Cid from Indra presented the project context, the consortium members, the project structure divided by work packages and progress made in the first 6 months of the

project. The workflow under which the consortium worked to extract the project requirements was presented.

After the presentation of the project to the audience the Demonstration workshop began. For each demonstration scenario, a brief description of the scenario has been provided, the potential related tools and potential data sources, the demonstration timeline, VALKYRIES Detected Opportunities and the Associated Technical Requirements. Teresa Martín from the - Medical Emergency Service SUMMA112 (SUM) presented the Demonstration Scenario #1: Spain-Portugal Major fire; Beáta Korpesio from the International Security and Emergency Management Institute (ISE) presented the Demonstration Scenario #2: Slovakia-Austria Factory accident with plumb spills; Yantsislav Yanakiev from the Bulgarian Defence Institute (BDI) presented the Demonstration Scenario #3: Bulgaria-Greece Earthquake; and Jon Herman from University of South-eastern Norway (USN) presented the Demonstration Scenario #4: Norway-The Netherlands-Denmark Ship accident.

Finally, the floor was given to the EAB members who introduced themselves to the audience and a discussion about the points covered during the day and the schedule and actions planned for the next months was carried out.

First VALKYRIES and Demonstration Workshops Agenda

March 30th – First VALKYRIES Workshop	
09:00 – 9:10	Welcome reception Indra
9:10 – 9:40	General VALKYRIES project presentation Indra
9:40 – 10:00	Q&A
10:00 – 10:15	Break
March 30th – First Demonstration Workshop	
10:15 – 10:35	Demonstration Scenario #1: Spain-Portugal Major fire SUMMA112 - Medical Emergency Service
10:35 – 10:55	Demonstration Scenario #2: Slovakia-Austria Factory accident with plumb spills International Security and Emergency Management Institute
10:55 – 11:15	Demonstration Scenario #3: Bulgaria-Greece Earthquake Bulgarian Defence Institute
11:15 – 11:35	Demonstration Scenario #4: Norway-The Netherlands-Denmark Ship accident University of South-eastern Norway
11:35 – 12:00	Discussion with EAB and Experts

Figure 11 – VALKYRIES and Demonstration Workshops Agenda

5.1.2. 1st Standardization Workshop

Novotec (NOV) carried out the first Standardization workshop on March 31th 2022. The event was held in virtual format and had the aim of bringing together main stakeholders from standardization bodies (NIST), Industrial stakeholders and universities, into an open discussion pointed to analysed to current status of the standardization of emergency services in terms of cross-sector a cross-border interoperability. In total there were 40 attendees who connected to the workshops, of which 22.5% were women.

During the open workshop discussion, Ignacio Hernandez from Novotec presented the progress of the project in the first 6 months.

After a brief welcome and introductions, he presented the project context, the harmonization and standardization methodology and the ongoing actions for this purpose. He explained the objectives, periodicity of the workshops and the agenda for this WS. This presentation was used to confirm that the project actions were aligned with international actions in terms of standardisation.

Afterwards a round table discussion took place, in which several project members and experts participated. In this open debate, ideas on standardisation and needs of first responders in an emergency were presented and discussed. The contributions helped to feed back the project and share knowledge. A fluent dialogue arose which adds value to the ongoing actions.

University of South-Eastern Norway (USN) was invited to lead a part of the meeting on Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities. Marius Stian introduced the University South of Norway's work on Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities within the project. He explained the ongoing actions and the work carried out so far in the project also to check that they were in line with European actions in terms of accreditation. Afterwards a round table served to share ideas between partners and experts.

First Standardization Workshop Agenda

March 31th – First Standardization Workshop

16:00 – 16:10	Welcome reception and presentations Novotec
16:10 – 16:40	Harmonisation and Standardisation Valkyries methodology Novotec
16:40 – 17:00	Discussion with EAB and Experts
17:00 – 17:15	Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities University South of Norway
17:15 – 17:20	Discussion with EAB and Experts

Figure 12 – Standardization Workshop Agenda

5.1.3. 1st Legal and Ethical Workshop

The first ethical legal workshop was included in the programme of the prestigious CPDP 2022 Conference <https://www.cpdpconferences.org/>, a world-leading multidisciplinary conference that offers the cutting edge in legal, regulatory, academic and technological development in privacy and data protection. Within an atmosphere of independence and mutual respect, CPDP gathers academics, lawyers, practitioners, policy-makers, industry and civil society from all over the world in Brussels and online.

The VALKYRIES panel was a blended one: almost 15 people attended in presence and 8 online.

Title: ***Transitional (Legal) Times for R&D and R&I Sectors***

Target: Academic ** Business ** Policy **

Panel Description

R&D and R&I sectors are currently affected by the European Strategy of Data as well as by the entering into application of EU legislative initiatives (Clinical Trials and Medical Device Regulations) and their balance with the ongoing debate on AI Regulation. The panel explores how the standardization and compliance processes will deal with the challenges and new obligations emerging by the uncertainties of the applicable ethical-legal framework in order to understand the possible domino effect produced by the GDPR towards the following EU initiatives aiming to enhance fundamental rights in the new technologies. Specific scenarios, investigated under the H2020 - VALKYRIES project as well (GA 101020676), will be discussed by the speakers, such as the development of AI solutions for first aid and multi-victim disasters, where health-related data are processed.

- Which are the most significant obligations for R&D and R&I emerging from the EU Strategy of Data framework and the already approved CTR, MDR, GDPR?
- What are the challenges in terms of standardization and compliance?
- How the proposal of AI Regulation will impact on the development of solutions
- Which specific safeguards shall be implemented in case of solutions processing health-related data for emergencies management?

The screenshot shows a Zoom meeting interface with four participants in the top bar: Daniel Pablo (...), Pedro Ramón (...), Owe Langfeldt..., and Andrea Parziale. The main content is a slide titled "SPEAKERS" with the VALKYRIES logo and the European Union flag. The slide lists four speakers:

Name and Affiliation	Biography
Pedro Ramón y Cajal Ramo (INDRA, VALKYRIES PC)	Cyber defence analyst at INDRA. Specialized in the legal, ethical and doctrinal issues surrounding military operations. With a special focus on those developed through cyberspace, where multiple actors are involved and sensitive information is shared. <i>Project illustration and need of standardization procedures (cross-border challenges and interoperability) for mapping emergencies, catastrophes and military operations</i>
Andrea Parziale, PhD (Maastricht Un.)	Currently Marie Skłodowska-Curie Fellow at the Institute for Transnational Legal Research at the Faculty of Law, Maastricht University. He worked as a post doc at Eurac Research (Bolzano, Italy) and Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies (Pisa, Italy). He obtained his Ph.D. from Sant'Anna School with a thesis on the civil liability for unauthorised yet lawful uses of medicines in the EU. <i>Ethical legal issues for patients: frontiers of biomedical research</i>
Rowena Rodrigues, PhD (Trilateral Research)	Head of Innovation & Research Services at Trilateral Research. She coleads and works to drive the growth of I&R services in defined strategic business areas. She carries out ethical, legal, and policy research related to new tech and provides regulatory, industry and policy advice. <i>Ethical legal issues of emergency responses with AI solutions</i>
Owe Langfeldt (EU Comm)	Legal and policy officer in the data protection Unit at EU Commission DG Justice and Consumers, on health and digital topics. He worked as legal officer in the supervision of EDPS, dealing with it and JHA areas. <i>GDPR CTR MDR AI from legal and policy officer perspective</i>

Figure 13 - Picture of the Legal and Ethical workshop

The interesting interdisciplinary discussion was the opportunity to promote VALKYRIES both with flyers that have been distributed in presence in Brussels in the Conference bag (almost 1500 copies) and to maintain the interest on the project thanks to the webpage dedicated to

the panel <https://www.cpdpconferences.org/cpdp-panels/transitional-legal-times-for-r-d-and-r-i-sectors>.

5.1.4. 2nd Legal and Ethical Workshop

The second ethical legal workshop is the opportunity to present and discuss the first release of the protocols for innovators. It will take place on September 29th, 2022, and will be reported in the next Impact creation report.

5.1.5. 2nd VALKYRIES, Demonstration and Standardization Workshops

The second VALKYRIES, Demonstration and Standardization workshops have been delayed to October 11th, 2022, and will be reported in the next Impact creation report. In these WSs it is expected to discuss with the EAB and other experts external to the project the results of the analysis of gaps and opportunities carried out in WP4, 5 and 6 during the last months, as well, as the progress made regarding the planning and definition of the 4 demonstration scenarios that will take place at the end of the project. In addition, the aspects related to the standardization processes in this context will be seen.

5.2. Scientific publications and conferences

The scientific production carried out by the VALKYRIES consortium has been divided in those published in journals and conferences.

5.2.1. Journals

The list of VALKYRIES journal publications of this reporting period is summarized in Table 9.

Title	Date of publication	Author(s)	Journal	DOI
From P4 medicine to P5 medicine: transitional times for a more human-centric approach to AI-based tools for hospitals of tomorrow	March 2022	Denise Amram, Arianna Cignoni, Tommaso Banfi, Gastone Ciuti	ORE	https://doi.org/10.145/3538969.3544482
VALKYRIES: Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Technology, Training and Tactical Coordinated Operations for First Responders on EU MCI	August 2022	Yantsislav Yanakiev, Marta Irene García Cid, Jorge Maestre Vidal, Nikolai Stoianov and Marco Antonio Sotelo Monge	ACM	https://doi.org/10.145/3538969.3544482

Table 9 – List of Journal Publications

5.2.2. Conferences and Congresses

Table 10 summarizes the list of conferences and congresses in which one or more consortium partners have made conference or poster contributions in this reporting period.

Title	Date and Country	Author(s)	Conference or congress name	Type of contribution
Conference on VALKYRIES Legal and Ethical issues	23-25 May 2022, Belgium	Denise Amram, Pedro Ramón y Cajal Ramo	15th International Conference on Computers, Privacy and Data Protection.	Conference/Round table

Title	Date and Country	Author(s)	Conference or congress name	Type of contribution
			https://www.cpdpconferences.org	
The VALKYRIES project	1-4 June 2022, Bulgaria	Rumen Daton, Yantsislav Yanakiev	XV International Defence Equipment and Services Exhibition (HEMUS). I Research and Innovation Symposium for European Security and Defence” (RISE-SD). https://rise-sd.net/projects-list	Conference/Stand
The VALKYRIES project	8-9 June 2022, Spain	Marta Irene García Cid	National emergency congress. https://cnemergencias.es/	Round Table

Title	Date and Country	Author(s)	Conference or congress name	Type of contribution
	<p>8-10 June 2022, Spain</p>	<p>A Montarelo Navajo, MC Martín Curto, CI Sierra Berrocal, D Bravo Montarelo, MI García Cid</p>	<p>XXXII SEMES National Congress. https://www.semes2022.org/index.php?idpagina=5&idioma=ca</p>	<p>Poster</p>
<p>VALKYRIES Project: Harmonized response to multi-casualty disasters in the European Union</p>				

Title	Date and Country	Author(s)	Conference or congress name	Type of contribution
<p>VALKYRIES: Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Technology, Training and Tactical Coordinated Operations for First Responders on EU MCI</p>	<p>23-26 Aug. 2022, Austria</p>	<p>Yantsislav Yanakiev, Marta Irene García Cid, Jorge Maestre Vidal, Nikolai Stoianov, Marco Antonio Sotelo Monge</p>	<p>III Workshop on Recent Advances in Cyber Situational Awareness on Military Operations (CSA) as part of the 17th International Conference on Availability, Reliability and Security (ARES) - Core B. https://www.ares-conference.eu/</p>	<p>Conference/Proceeding</p>

Title	Date and Country	Author(s)	Conference or congress name	Type of contribution

Table 10 – List of Conferences and Congresses

5.3. Liaison initiatives with other EU projects

In order to carry out a correct liaison strategy between sister European projects, the first step was to define what the consortium understood by liaison and the result was:

“The approach between two or more related European projects which lead to a synergy between them.”

The main purpose of establishing these points of contact between different EU projects is to maximize the efforts, discoveries and developments made by other consortiums trying to take advantage of previously done analysis, lessons learned, designs or even developments that enhance the results of VALKYRIES. In the same way, that the analyses and results from VALKYRIES can serve as input for other sister projects with similar topics, technologies or design decisions.

In *D1.9 Communication and Dissemination Strategies* a series of activities that could be classified as liaison activities were defined and some projects that could be possible candidates to analyse points of synergy were indicated. In this first year, we have made a series of approaches with some of these projects in which meetings and exchanges of information have been carried out to identify possible points of interest. The current status of these activities is summarized in Table 11.

In order to formalize the liaison activities and establish an agreement between the coordinators of the projects involved, a formalization document has been drawn up. This document consists of a description of VALKYRIES and its sister project, the synergies and points of interest detected between them, and the list of liaison activities to be carried out. This document is then reviewed and approved by the PCs.

Project	Coordinator	Framework	Status
UnCoVer (Link)	Institute of Tropical Medicine Antwerp	H2020	(02/03/2022) Presentation meeting between the projects and exchange of information and scientific paper. (On-going) VALKYRIES is analyzing the information received.
FIRE-RES (Link)	Centre de Ciència i Tecnologia Forestal de Catalunya	H2020	(01/06/2022) Presentation meeting with coordinator. (06/09/2022) Meeting with firefighters from Catalunya, Spain. Exchange of information and public deliverables. (On-going) FIRE-RES is analyzing the information received.
FIRE-IN (Link)	Association Pegase	H2020	(27/06/2022) Presentation meeting between the projects and exchange of information. (On-going) VALKYRIES is analyzing their Challenges and Resources matrix, in addition to D1.4 available in FIRE-IN website.
FASTER (Link)	The Centre for Research and Technology-Hellas (CERTH)	H2020	(05/04/2022) VALKYRIES Presentation in FASTER's final field drill. (28/06/2022) Meeting to define next steps to close the liaison activity already done. (14/09/2022) Signature of Liaison Official Document by PCs.
RESCUER (Link)	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	H2020	(22/06/2022) Presentation meeting between the projects and exchange of information (On-going) VALKYRIES and RESCUER are analyzing the information received.

Table 11 – Current status of the liaison activities with other EU projects

6. Next Actions

Ahead of the final impact creation report at M24, the consortium members have planned the actions bellow, bearing in mind their potential contribution in the project communication and dissemination goals.

Regarding the communication activities, the strategy addressed up to now will continue to be followed. The website and social networks will be updated with new content and improvements to increase the engagement of our followers and new visitors. Likewise, the remaining newsletters of the project will be published in M18 and M24. And the basic information of the project will continue to be spread among events through presentations and the communication materials (fact sheet, rollup, etc.). In the coming months, special effort will be put into planning the communication strategy for the final demonstrators of the project.

As to the dissemination activities, the consortium is committed with the conferences and publication of scientific papers describing the results obtained from the analysis phase of the project in terms of minimum dataset, design and development of testbeds, gaps and opportunities detected over the three work streams, and notable ethical-legal and standardization aspects. Specifically, for October 28th and 29th, 2002, the participation in the XXV Municipal Conference on Disasters in Spain is planned. In the same way, the planning of the second round of the Project Workshops is being completed, that is, the 2nd VALKYRIES, Standardization, Legal and Ethical and Demonstration workshops. In them, it is expected to increase the assistance from the EAB, as well as from external experts interested in the project.

Lastly, regarding the liaisons, in the first half of this year it is expected to close the analysis of synergies with at least 4 sister projects in order to later draw up the formalization documents to be approved by the coordinators and start, in the second half of the year, the execution of the defined and agreed activities.

7. Conclusions

This deliverable summarized the efforts undertaken by the VALKYRIES consortium pursuing the accomplishment of the communication and dissemination goals defined in the release of deliverable *D1.9 – Communication and Dissemination Strategies*.

During this first half of the project, the major emphasis has been put into the communication initiatives in order to create a project identity to attract the attention of stakeholders and experts from different fields of emergencies. Thus, the performed actions report started with those related with the organization and updates of the project website and a broad review of its initial statistics. In the same line, the tracked social media activity drawn an initial picture of its status, revealing an area of work to be boosted in the coming months. Besides this, VALKYRIES's coverage on the media has been reviewed, accounting press releases and external articles addressed to the general audience. The participation in events has also been appointed highlighting individual and joint partners' efforts to attend them making room for involving VALKYRIES within the participants. In general, the communication activities have followed the planning and the results have been as expected.

Regarding dissemination activities, the production of scientific content has been reported covering a proceeding and a poster publication and several conferences. These activities will take on greater relevance in the second half of the project since, after completing the analysis phase, the consortium has results and relevant information to be published in high-impact scientific journals and disseminated at conferences. Likewise, these results extracted from the analysis phase will be presented in the second round of project workshops that will take place at the end of M12. Finally, a note on liaison efforts took place as part of the reported action.

8. Annex A – References and bibliography

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9. Annex B – Glossary

Acronym	Description
AES	Asociación Española de empresas de Seguridad
ARES	Availability, Reliability and Security
C&D	Communication & Dissemination
CPDP	Computer Privacy and Data Protection
DX.X	Deliverable X.X
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FR	Funding Requirement
H2020	Horizon 2020
IA	Innovation Action
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MX	Month X
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
PC	Project Coordinator
PU	Public
QX	Quartile X
R	Report
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
TX.X	Task X.X
U.S.	United States
WP	Work Package
WS	Workshops

Table 12 - Glossary